

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SHOYOMBO****FIRST NAME: VICTORIA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The following statements highlight the differences between quantitative and qualitative research except**
 - Qualitative research follows participant perspectives to understand social events, settings or activities while quantitative research focuses on investigating associations, causal effect or relationship.
 - Qualitative uses triangulation to reduce misinterpretation and clarify meaning while quantitative uses random sampling to control for bias and allow for generalization.
 - In qualitative research there are no variables to focus on, the aim of the analysis is to discover and generate insight.
 - Only quantitative research requires complex data collection, analysis and assumptions.¹**

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles; SAGE, 2008), 78.

2. **According to Turabian rule of style which of these is not a type of research questions?**

- Contextual question.**²
- Conceptual question.
- Practical question.
- Applied research question.

3. **Which of the following statements best described a story board?**

- It extends over several pages but does not contain the research outline.
- It is a flexible outline that helps create a roadmap and tracks progress towards set goals.**³
- It is only useful for short dissertation and cannot be use for large writing projects.
- Although flexible and can be updated, you need to start afresh every time you make changes.

4. **Writing a draft report enhances the writer's critical ability. The following are tips for a successful draft except**

- Summarize when details are not important.
- Paraphrase if you can express the concept better in your own words.
- Quote evidence you agree with or a view that you disagree with.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 8th edition, Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

³ *Ibid.*, 22.

The first draft is the project outline and story board.⁴

5. **What is the correct citation for an online journal article when using the Turabian author-date reference style?**

Gubar, Susan. 2011. "In the Chemo Colony." *Critical Inquiry* 37, no. 4 (Summer): 652–71. Accessed August 29, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/660986>.⁵

Gubar Susan. 2011. "In the Chemo Colony." *Critical Inquiry* 37, no. 4 (Summer): 652–71. Accessed August 29, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/660986>.

Gubar, Susan. 2011. "In the Chemo Colony." *Critical Inquiry* 37, no. 4 (Summer): 652–71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/660986>.

Gubar, Susan. "In the Chemo Colony." *Critical Inquiry* 37, no. 4 (Summer): 652–71. Accessed August 29, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/660986>.

6. **Which of the quantitative school of thoughts advocate for an action agenda?**

Critical theory or advocacy.⁶

Social constructivism.

Post positivism.

Pragmatism.

⁴ Ibid., 44.

⁵ Ibid., 144..

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 8–9.

7. **What is the difference between methods and methodology?**

- Methods denotes specific techniques, procedures or tools used to generate data, methodology includes the research process and other logistics and ethical issues.⁷**
- Methods refers to data collection tools while methodology is the research design.
- Method uses only one data collection method while methodology is the use of multiple data collection tools.
- Methods is focused only on data collection, while methodology triangulates data to improve accuracy.

8. **Which of these is NOT correct for analysis and synthesis?**

- It provides key interpretation of findings.
- It is the process of converting data to information.
- Presents information in data summary tables.
- It is not focused on answering the research question.⁸**

9. **What are the components of a house style?**

- Spellings and punctuations.
- Terminology and formatting.
- Reference style.
- Dictionary.⁹**

⁷ Ibid., 73.

⁸ Ibid., 74.

⁹ World Health Organization (WHO). *WHO Style Guide*. (Geneva: WHO, 2004).

10. Which of these is not correct as regards EUCLID writing styles?

- Apply footnote and intext referencing for final paper¹⁰.**
- Apply footnote referencing for the QUIZ paper.
- Author-date Turabian referencing style is used for period papers.
- The recommended referencing style is Turabian.

¹⁰ Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period One*. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.

Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period One*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 8th edition. Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization (WHO). *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva, WHO 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.